

BEST PRACTICES OF YOGA IS A THERAPEUTIC TOOL FOR CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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Abstract

Children who have impairments who regularly engage in Yoga typically wow others with their rapid acquisition of diverse yoga practices, as well as significant enhancement of fundamental motor, linguistic, and cognitive abilities. They also cultivate heightened attention, balance, and control in their daily endeavors. Yoga offers benefits to everyone, as long as they receive good guidance and engage in consistent and committed practice. It is strongly advised that parents of special children also participate in yoga classes with their children to personally witness the benefits of yoga. Additionally, it facilitates the establishment of stronger emotional connections and comprehension between the parent and the child with special needs. While the exact consequence may be uncertain, it is clear that yoga has the ability to reconstruct, enhance, and redefine the kid, establishing a basis for positive advancement. Despite the utilization of contemporary medical methodologies to treat impairments, their efficacy has been limited. When compared to the treatment provided to these youngsters, yoga therapy has been determined to be more advantageous due to the unclear mechanism of action of many psychotropic medicines. However, it can be confidently stated that these practices genuinely bring individuals joy and happiness, resulting in a state of jubilation and enhancing their overall quality of life. Additionally, these practices provide them with a sense of well-being, in addition to other physical advantages. These children possess an extraordinary level of perception. They provide us with extensive knowledge about the unpleasant truths of existence. They embrace their existence as bestowed upon them by God, accepting everything with grace and without any grievances. They are the

unique manifestations of the incomprehensible cosmic drama orchestrated by the Divine. This paper focuses on the yoga practices and their benefits for children with special needs, as well as the role of parents in yoga teaching. It also examines the outcomes of yoga in promoting empowerment.

Keywords: Yoga, children with specific needs, parents, adaptability, benefits.

Introduction

Yoga is a holistic discipline that enhances both mental and physical well-being by promoting strength and flexibility. Additionally, it can aid with pain management and alleviate tension. Multiple forms of yoga include bodily poses, respiratory methods, and contemplation. Yoga is a time-honored discipline that encompasses physical postures, focused attention, and mindful respiration. Asana enhances physical strength, meditation enhances mental focus, and controlled breathing promotes relaxation and physical healing (Bhavanani, 2017). Consistently practicing yoga can enhance endurance, strength, tranquility, flexibility, and overall well-being. Yoga has gained widespread popularity as a form of exercise across the globe. The fundamental principle behind yoga is the integration of the mind, body, and spirit. Contemporary yoga emphasizes physical activity, muscular power, flexibility, and controlled respiration. It has the potential to enhance both physical and emotional well-being. Children with special needs exhibit a range of physical and mental problems that impact their psychological outlook. They have a deficiency in self-assurance and possess a negative perception of themselves. They experience emotions of inadequacy due to their recognition of their own oddity and lack of success in various aspects. They are experiencing frustration as a result of their incapacity to perform basic duties, either being unable to do so or encountering significant difficulties in doing so. Consequently, they experience high levels of tension and quickly become fatigued from physical effort. The rigidity of the spine causes significant discomfort, resulting in restricted mobility and disrupting the coordination of the limbs. They also experience challenges in maintaining focus. Children with disabilities who regularly engage in Yoga typically wow others with their rapid acquisition of diverse yoga practices, as well as significant enhancement of

fundamental motor, linguistic, and cognitive abilities. They cultivate heightened attention, balance, and control in their daily pursuits. Yoga has been proven to have therapeutic benefits for psychosomatic conditions including bronchial asthma (Nagarathna & Nagendra, 1985; Nagendra & Nagarathna, 1986). According to a study conducted by Uma, Nagarathna, Nagendra, Vaidehi, and Seethalakshmi in 1989, mentally retarded children experienced improvements in their general mental ability, psychomotor coordination, and intelligent and social behavior after practicing yoga for 9 months. Additionally, a study by M. Javnbakht and R. HejaziKenari in 2009 found that yoga has shown positive results in treating various physical and mental disorders. It is important to note that anyone can benefit from yoga, a It is strongly advised that parents of unique children also participate in yoga classes with their children to personally feel the benefits of yoga. Additionally, it facilitates the development of stronger emotional connections and comprehension between the parent and the child with special needs. Although the exact effect is uncertain, it is well-established that yoga has the ability to reconstruct, enhance, and redefine the kid, thereby establishing a basis for beneficial development.

Yoga Instruction

Yoga education can complement college education. It can enhance the physical and mental preparedness of students, allowing for the integration of their physical, mental, and spiritual abilities. This, in turn, enables students to become healthier, more balanced, and better integrated individuals within society and the nation. Yoga education fosters self-discipline and self-control, resulting in heightened awareness, focused concentration, and an elevated state of consciousness. Yoga education facilitates the development of optimal physical health, cultivates mental well-being, fosters emotional equilibrium, promotes the integration of ethical principles, and enables the attainment of elevated levels of awareness. Frequently, when patients undergo medical interventions, the emphasis is placed on their impairments and their diagnosis of a disease, with less consideration given to their general health and well-being (Wade and Halligan, 2017). It serves as an educational extension to the knowledge acquired in schools and universities. This education aims to equip students with the necessary

physical and mental abilities to integrate their physical, mental, and spiritual faculties. The goal is to enable students to become integrated members of society, possessing a calm and focused mindset through the practice of yoga and meditation.

Children with special needs

Children with Special Needs (CWSN) are those who possess a handicap of some kind and necessitate specialized care and additional assistance. The specific requirements of these youngsters are contingent upon the type of impairment they have. The unique requirements of Children with Special Needs (CWSN) may encompass regular medical examinations, extended hospital visits, specialized equipment, and necessary adjustments to accommodate their disability. They are individuals who are children and have a disability or a combination of disabilities that hinder their capacity to learn or engage in other activities. A kid is considered to have special educational needs if they possess a learning difficulty or impairment that hinders their ability to learn at a level comparable to their peers of the same age. They may have difficulties in academic performance, interpersonal communication, or behavioral conduct. Parents can seek assistance and guidance from experts, educators, and non-profit organizations.

Yoga for Children with Special Needs

An essential message conveyed by yoga is the importance of embracing oneself without judgment. Every individual possesses distinct characteristics, requirements, restrictions, and abilities. It is imperative that children with exceptional needs uncover their inherent greatness. Engaging in yoga enables individuals to explore their mind and body without any form of evaluation or criticism. They have the freedom to progress at their own pace, according to their own schedule. Yoga breathing, affirmations, mindfulness methods, and poses help youngsters develop the ability to focus on their inner guidance, intuition, and feel at ease in their physical body while silencing their self-critical thoughts. The non-competitive aspect of yoga fosters a sense of inclusivity among children, allowing them to feel accepted and capable of participating, regardless of their physical or mental capabilities. Individuals are motivated and advance based on their own commitment, concentration, and aptitude. Engaging in group practice fosters a

feeling of camaraderie and affiliation with the class, the community, and mankind as a whole. Children with exceptional needs can unlock their entire potential in terms of their emotional, intellectual, and physical capacities by developing an appreciation for their own unique qualities.

Advantages of yoga for children with unique needs

Teachers have been instructed to meet the increasing demands of pupils in their classrooms, as the number of students with special needs continues to rise each. Children with special disabilities may exhibit distinct behaviors that necessitate extra attention to classroom management. Yoga consists of three fundamental elements: the emotional aspect, which involves focusing on the breath; the physical aspect, which involves doing various poses; and the spiritual aspect, which involves engaging in meditation. Yoga encompasses various subcategories that prioritize specific characteristics above other elements. Yoga enhances physical attributes such as balance, flexibility, coordination, kinesthetic awareness, and motor skills. Yoga has a positive impact on children's emotional well-being by enhancing their ability to identify and manage their emotions, so fostering empathy and equipping them with effective strategies to alleviate distress or anger. Yoga enhances social interactions by fostering a sense of camaraderie and trust among individuals. Children who possess the ability to recognize and articulate their emotions are more adept at effectively communicating with their classmates. Cultivating empathy promotes a deeper comprehension and admiration for one's peers, hence cultivating more robust social connections. Yoga enhances mental faculties such as concentration, attention, and creativity. Acquiring these abilities promotes resilience and imparts youngsters with the required coping mechanisms to enhance their mental wellbeing. Yoga enables youngsters to investigate and cultivate their sense of self. Children with physical or mental disabilities are sometimes referred to as differently-abled children, and they may exhibit varying mental dispositions. Typically, children with special needs exhibit a deficiency in self-assurance and possess a diminished perception of themselves. They will possess knowledge of their abnormalities and experience a strong sense of inferiority compared to others. These children struggle with performing basic chores. Children with special

needs exhibit rigid spinal structures, resulting in restricted mobility, leading to worse balance and diminished limb coordination. Additionally, these children exhibit a deficiency in their capacity to concentrate. Children with special needs possess exceptional cognitive abilities and have the capacity to effortlessly grasp and rapidly acquire proficiency in every yoga step and position. Yoga enhances fundamental motor and cognitive abilities, enhances communication skills and focus, and improves balance and flexibility in everyday tasks. Engaging in yoga practice aids in diminishing the rigidity of the spine, thereby enhancing the body's alignment and equilibrium. It is beneficial for children with special needs to engage in yoga sessions with their parents in order to enhance their attachment and bonding. The advantages of engaging in yoga for children with special needs encompass the subsequent benefits:

- Yoga facilitates the synchronization of emotions, mind, and body.
- Enhances concentration and focus by reducing distractions.
- Enhance the efficiency of tasks performed in daily activities.
- Foster the autonomy of children with exceptional needs.
- Enhances social aptitude, interpersonal communication, and interpersonal connections, while diminishing emotional strain.
- Enhances positive behavior through the enhancement of social skills, self-assurance, and self-reliance.
- Enhances the integration of locomotor and psychomotor abilities.
- Reduces the prevalence of obesity.
- Enhances coordination.
- Enhances focus and prolongs the ability to concentrate.
- Reduces hostility.

- Reduce excessive levels of activity.
- Enhance the desire to eat.
- Enhance the circadian rhythm of sleep.
- Enhances the body's immune system.
- Enhances general well-being.
- Reduce reliance on drugs.
- Enhance the overall well-being of the neurological system.

The parental role in facilitating yoga practice for children with special needs.

Yoga is increasingly becoming popular as a comprehensive method for promoting well-being, not only for adults but also for children, including those with special needs. Currently, numerous parents are embracing yoga and engaging in it alongside their children, realizing that it is an excellent method to foster a strong connection with their offspring and establish a wholesome way of living for the entire family. When parents engage in yoga with their children, they not only participate in a physical exercise together, but also in a shared mental and emotional experience. Yoga provides a unique opportunity for parents to establish a bond with their children, fostering a feeling of proximity and emotional connection. Additionally, it offers parents a chance to demonstrate positive behaviors and effective methods for managing stress to their children. In addition to engaging in joint yoga sessions, parents can also foster their children's awareness in various other domains of their lives. Engaging in yoga sessions with children is an excellent method for parents to establish a strong connection with their offspring, instill positive habits, and enhance their overall physical and emotional state. Through the joint effort of parents and children, they can enhance their bond and fortify their relationship by engaging in physical and mental exercises.

Empowering via Yoga

The objective is not primarily to achieve proficiency in intricate postures, but rather to attain equilibrium, power, adaptability, and serenity within one's own limitations. Yoga serves as a means for individuals to cultivate self-acceptance, self-care, and empowerment by facilitating a novel connection with their bodies. Yoga for individuals with physical challenges enables them to gradually develop strength without experiencing strain or discomfort by adjusting each posture to accommodate their specific physical ailments or restrictions. This can be achieved by the use of props such as blocks or straps, or by changing motions. Essentially, yoga for individuals with physical disabilities promotes inclusivity by establishing a space that is welcoming to all individuals, irrespective of their capabilities. It encourages individuals to have a positive regard for themselves and cultivates a feeling of belonging among those who may have previously experienced exclusion from conventional exercise pursuits. There are limitless advantages to be gained by practicing yoga.

Common misunderstandings around Yoga for individuals with physical disabilities

Yoga has been increasingly popular as a potent exercise that can provide advantages to individuals of varying capabilities. Nevertheless, there are many prevalent misunderstandings regarding yoga for those with physical disabilities. Let us dispel these misconceptions and illuminate the truth. There is a common misconception that yoga is exclusively suitable for individuals who possess flexibility or physical prowess. This statement is completely false! Yoga is a practice that can accommodate and adjust to the specific requirements and constraints of each individual. The practice emphasizes the connection between the mind and body, incorporates breath control, and teaches relaxation methods, ensuring that it is suitable for all individuals. Another fallacy is that engaging in yoga with disabilities or physical limitations may result in injury or worsen pre-existing conditions. Yoga, when done with the guidance of a professional and customized to individual limitations, can enhance strength, flexibility, balance, and overall well-being. Furthermore, there is a common assumption that adaptive yoga courses are deficient in terms of both diversity and intensity when compared to standard programs. However, the opposite is true! Adaptive yoga instructors possess the knowledge and skills to adjust yoga postures according to the varying abilities of their

students, ensuring a stimulating and customized experience that aligns with each individual's potential. It is crucial to debunk these misunderstandings so that those with physical limitations feel empowered to confidently explore the advantages of yoga. Under the leadership of skilled instructors who have expertise in providing adapted sessions, individuals of all physical abilities can benefit from this ancient discipline.

The Significance of Flexibility in a Yoga Practice

Flexibility is crucial for any yoga session, but it is especially important for persons facing physical limitations. Adaptability, in this sense, pertains to the act of adapting and adjusting yoga postures and sequences to cater to the specific requirements and constraints of individual practitioners. The primary rationale for the importance of adaptation in a yoga practice for those with physical challenges is the inherent variability of each person's body. Individuals may possess distinct physical restrictions or conditions that necessitate adjustments. Through the use of flexibility, teachers can guarantee that each participant experiences a sense of inclusion and empowerment throughout their practice. Moreover, versatility enables practitioners to operate at their preferred speed and level of ease. It motivates individuals to pay attention to their body and modify their actions accordingly. This facilitates the promotion of safety and cultivation of self-awareness, enabling those with physical limitations to discover the most effective strategies for their pursuit of well-being. Adaptability in a yoga practice goes beyond just making changes to poses; it also entails fostering an inclusive environment that provides support to all practitioners. Yoga instructors who prioritize adaptation create a setting where students feel comfortable asking questions, expressing problems, or seeking extra help without any reluctance. By embracing adaptability in a yoga practice, those with physical limitations can enjoy the various advantages of frequent involvement, such as enhanced strength, flexibility, balance, and improved mental well-being. This approach also acknowledges and respects their specific circumstances.

Conducting Adaptive Yoga Classes

The crucial aspect of instructing adaptive yoga courses is to establish a secure and all-encompassing environment that accommodates individuals with diverse abilities for their practice. As an instructor, it is crucial to have a profound comprehension of various physical limits and their potential impact on students' movements and poses. An effective method for instructing adaptive yoga involves emphasizing the use of modifications. The practice of yoga has been found to have a substantial positive impact on relationships and a wide range of social, emotional, behavioral, and cognitive processes. This, in turn, can lead to improved cognitive function in children with Neurodevelopmental disorders, as supported by research conducted by Grensman et al. (2018) and Diamond and Lee (2011). This entails providing modified versions of conventional poses that are more easily attainable for individuals with physical limitations. For instance, accessories such as blocks or straps can enhance support and stability while performing balancing postures. Moreover, have the ability to adjust as an educator is of utmost importance. Individuals with limited mobility encounter more obstacles to engaging in regular physical activity compared to individuals without mobility limitations (Carroll et al., 2014; Damush et al., 2007; Martin, 2013; Newitt, Barnett, and Crowe, 2016). Each pupil will possess distinct requirements and constraints, thus it is crucial to maintain an open-minded attitude and devise innovative remedies when required. This may entail modifying the order of steps or offering extra instructions for particular actions. Effective communication is essential in adaptive yoga classes. It is crucial to establish effective communication channels with your pupils to ensure that they feel at ease in communicating their wants or problems during the session.

The Outcomes of Regular and Persistent Training

During the practice of Hatha Yoga, individuals will observe an enhancement in muscular strength and tone, leading to a more harmonized and stable lifestyle. Yoga for individuals with physical disabilities also emphasizes the practice of controlled breathing. The majority of individuals engage in the act of inhaling and exhaling

without conscious awareness. Gulati et al. (2018) proposed that a longer duration of yoga treatment leads to beneficial transformations in various aspects such as health, sensory perception, communication, and sociability. They also discovered that just two weeks of yoga therapy had a favorable impact on the behavior, aggression, and tranquility of children diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder. Yoga instructs in the practice of specialized breathing techniques, known as pranayama, which effectively enhance the strength of the lungs. Indeed, it is a fact that individuals of all abilities, even those with unique physical requirements, may engage in regular physical activity. Engaging in Yoga with proper precautions will enhance equilibrium, synchronization, respiration, and general well-being for all individuals involved.

Conclusion

Yoga is highly adaptable, allowing for modifications of poses to accommodate children who may struggle with particular positions. Teachers can gradually introduce more challenging poses to their students as they demonstrate the necessary capability. Various facets of yoga can yield distinct advantages for diverse categories of practitioners. Deep breathing can be highly beneficial for students struggling with emotional control, as it aids in calming them down during periods of distress. The meditation component of yoga offers advantages for pupils with attention deficit disorder, autism, or depression by enhancing concentration and focus. Additionally, it imparts mindfulness to youngsters, promoting empathy and resilience. Utilizing deep breathing techniques can also be beneficial for children who suffer from asthma or other respiratory challenges. Teaching children yoga is not only advantageous for their physical growth, but it is also essential for their emotional development and overall welfare. Incorporating yoga into the health and physical education curriculum facilitates the holistic development of children, encompassing their emotional, physical, and social well-being, while also promoting positive mental health. Teaching children yoga enhances their physical literacy by introducing them to various movements that they may then incorporate into other activities. As children get more confident, the complexity of the yoga postures can be adjusted to meet their specific needs. There are no impediments to engaging in the practice of yoga. Yoga can be practiced by individuals of any age, gender, disability, or

sickness. Yoga can be beneficial for children with special difficulties as it enhances their focus, cognitive abilities, and physical stability. Engaging in yoga can enhance self-assurance in children with impairments and enhance their capacities to communicate and interact with others. Additionally, it aids in reducing the mental distress experienced by these children. Yoga enhances posture by alleviating spinal rigidity.

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